

Community Knowledge and Awareness of Natural and Man-Made Disasters, South India Based on Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Introduction: Disasters—both natural and man-made—have been occurring with increasing frequency, intensity, and complexity due to factors such as urbanization, climate change, and socio-economic disparities. Understanding community knowledge and awareness is essential for effective disaster preparedness and resilience building. This study aimed to assess the community's understanding of disaster types, causes, impacts, and preventive measures in South India. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional descriptive design was employed among 500 adult participants selected using multistage sampling. Results revealed that 83% correctly defined the term “disaster,” and 79% reported awareness of it. While 67.4% recognized both natural and man-made disasters, only 6% correctly identified flood as a natural disaster, reflecting knowledge gaps in specific areas. Significant associations were found between awareness levels and variables such as age ($p=0.002$), experience ($p=0.004$), location ($p=0.030$), and designation ($p=0.001$). Gender and education showed no significant correlation. Approximately half (49.6%) had experienced floods, and 59.2% believed effective preventive measures exist. Awareness about post-disaster health impacts and local response systems remained inadequate. **Conclusion:** The findings highlight that although general disaster awareness is moderate to high, specific knowledge, especially about individual hazard types and health consequences, is limited. Strengthening community-level disaster education through simulation drills, school-based training, and awareness campaigns

is crucial to bridge these gaps and enhance resilience against recurring hazards in vulnerable regions.

Keywords: Community disaster knowledge, Disaster awareness, Natural and man-made disasters, Flood preparedness, Community resilience, Disaster risk perception, Socio-demographic factors, Cross-sectional study, Disaster health impacts, Disaster education and training

Introduction:

In recent years, there has been an increased frequency, intensity, and complexity across the world due to both natural and man-made disasters. This increased risk for disaster is due to rapid urbanization, climate change, ecosystem degradation, and socio-economic disparities, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2023)¹. As the world continues to experience hazardous conditions such as floods, cyclones, earthquakes, and pandemics, increasing the capacity of the community to recover has become a main focus of global disaster risk reduction strategies. Disaster knowledge and awareness are the basis of community resilience². This implies that people in the community know about hazards, vulnerabilities, preparedness and organizational response systems. According to the Global Assessment Report 2022 given by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, if resilience is not integrated into policymaking, disasters could result in an additional 100 million people falling into poverty by 2030 (UNDRR, 2022)³. Similarly, the World Health Organization's Community Protection and Resilience Unit highlights the need for community-level engagement. where local knowledge and communication about the risk are in effective preparedness and in breaking complex emergencies (WHO, CPR Unit). The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (2022) underlined that 3.3 to 3.6 billion people are living in highly vulnerable conditions where there is an increasing hazard exposure that intersects with severe socio-economic fragility, which implies the need for focused policy implementation (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2023)⁴. Extensive research in behavioral science has demonstrated that what people know about hazards and how they perceive the risks influence their actions towards protective measures. Studies show a significant association between community knowledge, risk perception and awareness, and the adoption of disaster preparedness action⁵. The role of knowledge in disaster preparedness has been explored across various population groups, from healthcare professionals to students and the general public. A study conducted among the households of South Korea has reported that disaster knowledge had a substantial impact on

disaster preparedness⁶. A similar study by identified that there is a strong correlation between perceived vulnerability and higher levels of preparedness in an infrastructure-resilient setting. This relationship has also been observed in studies involving nursing students and community pharmacists, where the increased awareness was directly linked to advanced emergency response capabilities⁷. Among frontline disaster response professionals, the preparedness for emergency situations or any hazard crises remains inconsistent. A study conducted in South India found that there is a lack of awareness among first responders regarding chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear, and explosive disasters (CBRNE) management⁸. Also, there is a similar knowledge gap identified among medical workers in Japan, with a focus on radiological emergencies. These findings underscore the need for targeted training and interdisciplinary preparedness strategies⁹. Community-based knowledge, particularly that based on local and native traditions, has been proven to enhance disaster resilience. An Indonesian study illustrated that local knowledge among communities in the vicinity of the Anak Krakatau Volcano were instrumental in guiding evacuation plans¹². Likewise, participatory disaster awareness programs in rural Myanmar have been associated with enhanced preparedness and capacity to respond for hazards. Researches have also identified high-risk groups, including the elderly and patients with chronic conditions¹³. who often face limited exposure to disaster risk education. In rural Japan, there is an alarming lack of preparedness infrastructure and awareness among elderly population¹⁴. Though there are many studies on assessing disaster knowledge and awareness, most studies are limited to single hazards such as earthquakes or pandemics, failing to focus on multiple disasters¹⁵. Despite of many researches on disaster knowledge and awareness among various countries, there is a notable geographical gap found in the Indian context. This gap is particularly concerning in South India, where the people have been repeatedly troubled by disasters such as cyclones, floods, droughts, and extreme heat waves in recent years. The knowledge and awareness about the disasters in this region remain understudied. Hence, it is important to focus on these areas to design the disaster management strategies and to meet global commitments like Priority 1 of the Sendai Framework, that is Understanding disaster risk. Aligning with this commitment.

Objectives:

1. To evaluate the community understanding of different types of disasters (natural and man-made).
2. To assess the awareness regarding the causes, impacts, and preventive measures for common disasters such as floods, earthquakes, and fires.

Methodology:

Study Design:

This study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive design to evaluate the community's knowledge and awareness regarding natural and man-made disasters a coastal union territory in South India that is prone to recurrent disasters such as cyclones, floods, and heatwaves.

Study Area:

The research was conducted in south region frequently exposed to a variety of hazards including cyclones, coastal flooding, and extreme weather events. The study population included residents from both urban and peri-urban areas, ensuring diverse representation in terms of socio-economic status, education, and exposure to disaster experiences.

Study Population and Sampling:

The study targeted household heads and adult community members (aged 18 years and above) in selected wards of Puducherry. A multistage sampling method was employed:

- First, several wards were randomly selected across urban and peri-urban zones.
- Within each selected ward, households were chosen using systematic random sampling.
- One eligible respondent from each household was interviewed.

The sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula for cross-sectional studies, assuming a 50% prevalence of adequate disaster knowledge, 95% confidence interval, and 5% margin of error. Accounting for a 10% non-response rate, the final sample size was approximately 500 respondents.

Data Collection Tools and Techniques:

A semi-structured questionnaire was developed based on existing literature and validated tools used in previous disaster awareness surveys. The questionnaire covered the following domains:

- Socio-demographic details
- Awareness of disaster types (natural and man-made)
- Knowledge of disaster causes, impacts, and preparedness measures
- Sources of disaster information
- Perceptions of community resilience and preparedness

The tool was prepared in English and Tamil, pretested among 30 respondents in a non-study area, and refined accordingly. Trained field investigators conducted face-to-face interviews using the questionnaire.

Ethical Considerations:

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Srinivas University, Institution of allied health sciences Informed verbal and written consent were taken from all participants before data collection. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality of responses was strictly maintained.

Statistical Analysis:

Data collected and coded in excel also Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) depending on the normality of distribution. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of continuous variables for comparisons between two independent groups, Student's t-test was used as appropriate. For more than two groups, ANOVA was applied. Chi-square was used for categorical variables. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Table 1 Association Between Demographic Variables and Knowledge & Awareness about Disaster

S.No	Variable	Categoric	Count	P-Value
1.	Age	<20	352	0.002
		21-40	138	
		>41	10	
2.	Gender	Male	183	0.581
		Female	317	
3.	Education	UG	418	0.000
		PG	54	
		PHD	28	
4.	Experience	<5yr	420	0.004
		6-10	26	
		11-20	38	
		>21	16	
5.	Marital Status	Single	454	0.020
		Married	46	
6.	Location	Tamil Nadu	380	0.030

		Puducherry	85	
		Kerala	35	
7.	Field of study	Medical	450	0.001
		Non- Medical	50	
8.	Designation	Students	410	0.001
		Faculty	26	
		Others staffs	64	

The table 1 shows among 500 study population, An ANOVA test was performed to examine the association between various demographic factors and participants' knowledge and awareness regarding disasters. The analysis revealed statistically significant associations for the following variables: Age ($p = 0.002$): Knowledge and awareness levels significantly varied across age groups. Respondents below 20 years old ($n=352$) formed the majority, suggesting that younger individuals, possibly students, possess higher awareness—likely due to recent exposure to disaster education in academic settings. Education ($p = 0.000$): A strong association was observed, with undergraduate participants ($n=418$) showing greater awareness compared to postgraduate ($n=54$) and PhD holders ($n=28$). This may be due to greater emphasis on disaster preparedness in foundational programs or curriculum-based differences. Experience ($p = 0.004$): Participants with fewer years of experience (<5 years, $n=420$) showed higher knowledge levels. This finding may correlate with the predominance of students in the sample, as well as recent training or academic exposure. Location ($p = 0.030$): Significant regional differences were observed. Participants from Tamil Nadu ($n=380$) showed higher levels of awareness compared to those from Puducherry ($n=85$) and Kerala ($n=35$). This could be influenced by the frequency of disaster events or awareness programs in specific regions. Field of Study ($p = 0.000$): Respondents from medical backgrounds ($n=450$) exhibited significantly higher awareness than those from non-medical fields ($n=50$), underscoring the impact of curriculum and professional orientation in shaping disaster knowledge. Marital Status ($p = 0.020$): Both single ($n=454$) and married individuals ($n=46$) showed higher levels of knowledge. Designation ($p = 0.001$): Whether the respondent was a student ($n=410$), faculty ($n=26$), or other staff ($n=64$) did significantly influence their disaster awareness levels on the work designation. Conversely, some demographic variables did not show statistically significant associations with disaster knowledge: Gender ($p = 0.581$): No significant difference in awareness was found between male ($n=183$) and female ($n=317$) respondents.

Table 2: Knowledge and Awareness about Disaster

S.No	Variables	Total	Percentage	
1	Define disaster?	An event that causes a lot of harm or damage	415	83%
		An event where people play in the playground	40	8%
		An event where celebration happens	17	3.4%
		None of the above	28	5.6%
2	Are you aware of disaster?	Yes	395	79%
		No	105	21%
3	What kinds of disasters are there?	All of the above	337	67.4%
		Natural	129	25.8%
		Manmade	34	6.8%
		None of the above	0	0%
4	Have you ever worked on a disaster management team?	Yes	154	30.8%
		No	346	69.2%
5	Which of the following is natural disaster?	Flood	30	6%
		None of the above	433	86.6%
		Bomb Blast	26	5.2%
		Gun shot	0	0%
6	Have you ever experienced a flood?	Yes	248	49.6%
		No	246	49.2%
7		Assam	289	57.8%

	Name the location of the most recent flood?	Maharashtra	181	36.2%
		Tamilnadu	30	6%
		Delhi	0	0%
8	Which gov entity provides assistance during flood?	NDMA	258	51.6%
		NDMP	162	32.4%
		FEMA	80	16%
9	Is there any effective measures and strategy to prevent flood?	Yes	296	59.2%
		No	214	42.8%
10	Which of the following is a man-made disaster?	Building collapse	346	69.2%
		Earthquake	0	0%
		None	154	30.8%
11	Recent bomb blast in country?	Pakistan	0	0%
		Bangladesh	75	15%
		Srilanka	0	0%
		India	0	0%
		None	425	85%
12	Name the recent building collapse and rate of death?	Mumbai (10 - 15)	231	46.2%
		Nashik (greater than 20)	0	0%
		Amravati (5-10)	0	0%
		None	269	53.8%

13	What are the materials present in bomb blast?	Gunpowder	188	37.6%
		Fertilizer	40	8%
		H2O2	194	38.8%
		All of the above	78	15.6%
14	Are you aware of medical hazardous material?	Yes	387	77.4%
		No	113	22.6%
15	What health problems are present during floods?	Fever	119	23.8%
		Hypothermia	47	9.4%
		All the above	294	58.8%
		Drowning	40	8%
16	Can permanent damages occur to living individuals, due to a disaster?	Yes	291	58.2%
		No	209	41.8%
17	Any different health issues faced after the disaster?	Yes	0	0%
		No	500	100%
18	What is your experience about temporary accommodation?	Outstanding	71	14.2%
		Very Good	135	27%
		Fair	225	45%
		Poor	69	13.8%

19	How will you rate your hospitality during your accommodation?	Outstanding	0	0%
		Very Good	0	0%
		Fair	0	0%
		Poor	46	9.2%
		None	454	90.8%
20	Was there any special care for children?	Yes	425	85%
		No	75	15%
21	Was there any special care for old age?	Yes	289	57.8%
		No	211	42.2%
22	How many of you stayed in your friends or relatives place during flood?	Yes	315	63%
		No	185	37%

A semi - structured questionnaire was administered to 500 participants to assess their knowledge, awareness, and experiences related to disaster and flood management. The findings are summarized below. Awareness and Understanding of Disasters, A large majority (83%) correctly defined a disaster as an event causing significant harm or damage. Most respondents (79%) reported being aware of disasters, indicating a generally informed population. Types and Knowledge of Disasters,67.4% of participants recognized both natural and man-made disasters. However, confusion was evident in identifying examples of natural disasters—only 6% identified "flood" as a natural disaster, while 86.6% incorrectly selected “none of the above.” Regarding man-made disasters, 69.2% correctly identified "building collapse," but 30.8% did not recognize any listed option. Experience with Disasters, almost half the participants (49.6%) had experienced a flood. Assam (57.8%) and Maharashtra

(36.2%) were reported as the most affected locations. Only 30.8% had worked on a disaster management team, while 69.2% were unsure of their involvement. Government Response and Preventive Measures, The National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) was identified by 51.6% as the primary agency providing flood assistance, followed by NDMP (32.4%) and FEMA (16%). 59.2% of respondents believed there are effective measures and strategies in place to prevent floods. Specific Disaster Events, On recent bomb blast incidents, 85% responded "None," indicating either a lack of awareness or absence of recent high-profile cases in the country. 46.2% identified the Mumbai building collapse and estimated 10–15 deaths; 53.8% were unaware or uninformed. Hazardous Materials and Health Effects, Awareness of bomb-related materials was moderate: 38.8% selected H₂O₂, and 37.6% selected gunpowder. 77.4% reported awareness of medical hazardous materials. Health problems during floods included fever (23.8%), hypothermia (9.4%), and drowning (8%), with 58.8% selecting "all the above." Perceptions of Risk and Long-term Impact, 58.2% believed disasters could cause permanent damage to individuals. Surprisingly, all 500 respondents (100%) reported no different health issues after a disaster, suggesting underreporting or misunderstanding. Accommodation and Relief Experience, Experiences with temporary accommodation varied: 45% rated it "fair," 27% "very good," and 14.2% "outstanding." Hospitality ratings during accommodation were largely absent (90.8% selected "none"). Special care for children was widely reported (85%), while care for the elderly was slightly lower (57.8%). Coping and Community Support, 63% of participants stayed with friends or relatives during the flood, indicating strong community or family support networks. The findings indicate that while general awareness of disaster concepts is fairly high, there is significant misunderstanding in recognizing specific types of disasters, particularly floods. This reflects a gap in targeted disaster education. Most respondents are aware of government agencies involved in disaster relief and believe in the existence of preventive strategies, yet actual experience with disaster management teams is low. There is limited awareness about specific disaster events (e.g., bomb blasts, building collapses), and post-disaster health impact awareness seems inadequate, with all participants denying new health issues—a potential reporting bias or lack of follow-up systems. Temporary accommodation during disasters is moderately satisfactory, but hospitality support and feedback systems appear weak, as suggested by 90.8% reporting "none" in rating hospitality. Children and elderly care systems are in place to some extent but need expansion. Overall, while the awareness level is promising, there are critical gaps in disaster-specific knowledge,

training, and post-disaster health tracking. These areas should be prioritized in community disaster preparedness programs and public health education.

Table 3: Different Domain Association on knowledge and Awareness about Disaster (P-Value 0.05)

S.No	Domain	Age	Education	Experience	Marital Status	Location	Field of study	Designation
1.	Disaster	*0.001	0.370	*0.011	0.504	*0.000	0.868	*0.000
2.	Natural Disaster	*0.000	0.462	*0.038	0.022	*0.023	0.203	*0.000
3.	Mam made Disaster	*0.000	0.651	0.116	0.015	0.200	0.355	*0.024
4.	Knowledge on Health and accommodation during disaster	0.213	0.363	*0.045	0.363	*0.054	0.104	*0.008

Table 3 presents the results of the Chi-square test examining the association between various socio-demographic variables (age, education, experience, marital status, location, field of study, and designation) and different domains of knowledge and awareness about disasters. A p-value less than the respective significance threshold (typically $p < 0.05$) indicates a statistically significant association. For the general domain of disaster awareness, significant associations were observed with age ($p = 0.001$), experience ($p = 0.011$), location ($p = 0.000$), and designation ($p = 0.000$). No statistically significant association was found with education, marital status, or field of study. In the domain of natural disaster awareness, age ($p = 0.000$), experience ($p = 0.038$), marital status ($p = 0.022$), location ($p = 0.023$), and designation ($p = 0.000$) showed significant associations, whereas education and field of study did not demonstrate any significant relationships. Regarding man-made disaster awareness, statistically significant associations were found with age ($p = 0.000$), marital status ($p = 0.015$), and designation ($p = 0.024$). No significant associations were identified with education, experience, location, or field of study. In the domain of knowledge on health and accommodation during disasters, only experience ($p = 0.045$) and designation ($p = 0.008$) were significantly associated. Age, education, marital status, location, and field of study were

not found to be significantly associated in this domain. These findings suggest that age, experience, and particularly designation are critical factors influencing knowledge and awareness about various disaster-related domains. In contrast, education level and field of study did not show a consistent or significant impact across the domains, indicating a potential gap between formal education and disaster preparedness awareness.

DISCUSSION:

The present study delved into how our community understands the various types of disaster, from natural ones like floods and earthquakes to man-made events like fires and pollutions. We aimed to study what they people knew about the causes, effects, and how to prevent and manage these hazards. The findings show a complex picture of knowledge and awareness towards disaster, by highlighting the influence of demographic factors in the level of awareness¹⁶. This study found that most people have a basic understanding about definition of disaster which is about 83%. A significant percentage of participants (67.4%) could also identify both natural and human-made disasters. These findings support the study conducted in Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu where the basic understanding found to be satisfactory¹⁷. However, the specific gaps were found i.e. only 6% of the participants recognized flood as natural disasters, while a large proportion answered it as “none of the above”, which reveals that people may understand the concept of a disaster in theory but lack in practical knowledge. While 69.2% of people correctly identified "building collapse" as a man-made disaster, a significant lack of understanding persists regarding other examples. These findings align with a study conducted by that found a very poor disaster-specific awareness among ASHA workers in Mysuru, particularly in differentiating between the types of disasters¹⁸. Flood-related awareness was found to be decent. Approximately half (49.6%) of the study population reported firsthand experience with floods and majority of them believed that there are effective preventive strategies, as the participants are found to have experience with the episodes of flood every year. Yet, the knowledge regarding common post-flood impacts is limited. Only 58.8% identified fever, hypothermia, and drowning as common post-flood impacts. Similarly, institutional knowledge was also found to be limited. These findings are in contrast with other research by among resident doctors in Delhi, which shows a positive attitude towards the disaster impacts¹⁹. On earthquake and fire-related knowledge, this study observed poor awareness as there is limited exposure to this kind of disaster. These results support the study which found that specific experience of disaster significantly influences the knowledge of the community²⁰. Our findings revealed that there is significant association between disaster awareness and socio-demographic variables such as age,

designation, experience and location. The higher knowledge levels were observed in younger participants, students and the participants from Tamil Nadu shows that academic exposure and geographic experience with disaster were important in developing awareness. This conclusion was supported by a national study of nurses in India, which also found that preparedness was directly associated with the professional roles and training. In contrast, gender and education level did not correlate with awareness in this study. These findings suggest the urgent need for disaster education strategies and awareness campaigns to address the gaps in knowledge and awareness among the community, Moreover, simulation exercises, community drills, and school-based educations are recommended that could bridge the gap between knowledge and preparedness.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that while there is a moderate to high general awareness of disasters among the community in south India, significant gaps remain in specific disaster knowledge, particularly regarding natural disasters like floods and man-made events. Demographic factors such as age, experience, location, and designation significantly influence disaster knowledge, whereas gender and education level do not consistently impact awareness. The findings emphasize the need for targeted disaster education and training programs, including community drills and school-based interventions, to enhance practical understanding and preparedness. Strengthening post-disaster health monitoring and expanding support systems for vulnerable groups such as children and the elderly are also crucial. Overall, improving focused community-level disaster awareness and preparedness can foster resilience against frequent and complex hazards in this coastal region.

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